
Plan Overview

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: Data Management Plan for using the 'European Sustainable Workforce Survey'

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Template: UU Data Management Plan (DMP)

Project abstract:

Re-use of the data of the European Sustainable Workforce Survey Wave 1, 2 and 3, for the research articles:

- 'Workplace Variation in Migrant Job Searches: Cohesion Unities, Bonuses do not Divide'
- 'Quit Happens: Unravelling Which Behaviors and Attitudes of Co-Workers Trigger Turnover Contagion'
- 'From Erosion to Adaptation: How Collective Job Searches Undermine Cooperation Before, but not After COVID-19'

It is a three level cross-sectional dataset, collected by Utrecht University. Three waves were collected. The first in 2016, the second in 2018 and the third in 2024.

The ESWS has as main goal to contribute to a better understanding of what works for realizing a sustainable (future) workforce. It is a unique data collection project as it contains information at three levels. At the individual level, employees were asked a range of questions resulting in information on for example employee productivity, satisfaction, cooperation and work-life balance. At team-level, the data includes information on both team characteristics such as team cohesion and team productivity, and information on team managers such as their well-being. At the organizational level, the data includes information on characteristics of the establishment, with topics such as employer investments in employees, organizational policies and organizational culture.

ID: 175089

Start date: 04-04-2022

End date: 04-05-2025

Last modified: 04-04-2025

Data Management Plan for using the 'European Sustainable Workforce Survey'

Data Collection

1.1 Will you re-use existing data ?

If yes: explain which existing data you will re-use and under which terms of use.

- Yes, I will re-use existing data

We will use the data that was collected in the Netherlands of Wave 1, Wave 2 and Wave 3 of the European Sustainable Workforce Survey.

It is a three level survey with information on employees, teams/managers and organizations.

For the first wave, 2,485 employees in 156 teams and 48 organizations were included. For the second wave, 864 employees in 65 teams and 20 organizations were included. For the third wave, 2,023 employees in 128 teams and 45 organizations were included. This comes down to a combined total of 5,372 respondents from 348 teams and 112 organizations.

1.2 Describe your data.

Fill the table below with a brief description of the data, including the type, format and volume.

#	Data Description	Data Type	Format	Total Volume
1	Survey Data	Tabular	.csv	3,29 MB

Data Documentation

2.1 Describe the documentation and metadata that you will use to to make your data reproducible and interoperable. Describe which files you will provide, along with a brief description of the information they will contain, to make your data reproducible and interoperable. Describe the information that you will provide to make the data items in questions 2.1 reusable and interoperable. If using a specific metadata standard, please mention this below.

We will provide syntax files of SPSS for the editing of the data in order to make the raw data suitable for analyses.

Also, for some studies, we have STATA syntax for the analyses of the data, which we will provide as well. We will not store or share the data, as it is not in our ownership. Therefore, when accessing the raw data (which are to be requested from Principal Investigators Tanja van der Lippe and Anne van der Put), both syntax files suffice to reproduce our study. For methodological justification, we provide all surveys from all waves and all levels, and the codebooks (including research design, informed consent, etc.).

2.2 Describe the folder structure you will provide to make your data reproducible and interoperable. Describe the folder structure, naming conventions and/or version control you will use for this project.

The Data will be stored at the personal and protected U-Drive.

A separate folder is created for 'ESWS' in which both data and syntax files are stored.

Data Storage

3.1. Select the storage solution(s) where you will store and back-up your data.

Select the locations where your data will be stored. You may select more than one. Please describe the storage solution and the backup strategy of your storage solution if it does not appear in the list below.

- O:Drive

Data Privacy and Security

4.1 Will you be collecting or using personal data ?

Personal data is any data which, alone or in combination with other information, can identify a living person. Such data must abide by the GDPR and requires additional safeguards and documentation to be processed lawfully.

- Yes, I will collect and/or use personal data

Data abides by GDPR and went through Ethical Review. It is also fully anonymized.

4.2 What is the legal basis by which you are collecting and/or processing this data ?

If you are uncertain as to which legal basis applies to your type of research please do not hesitate to contact us at info.rdm@uu.nl or by using the "Request feedback" button and leaving a comment alongside this question.

- Informed consent

4.3 Select the privacy and security measures you will employ to protect the privacy of your data subjects. Check all that apply.

- Pseudonymization
- Secure storage

4.4 Who is the controller of the personal data ?

The controller of the personal data is the entity which determines what is done with the data. In most cases the

controller is Utrecht University.

Utrecht university is the controller of the collected personal data. Nevertheless, the principal investigator of the research project will ensure that the data is handled and processed in accordance with the GDPR.

4.5 How will ownership and intellectual property rights of the data be managed?

Describe who controls access to the data and who determines what is done to the data.

The Principal Investigators control access to the data and determine what is done to the data (based upon agreement with respondents and ethical review).

Data Selection, Preservation & Sharing

5.1 Describe the data you will be preserving and the storage solution where it will be preserved?

Describe which data will be preserved under long-term storage. You may refer back to the data described in question 1.2 to specify which data will be preserved. Explain where you will preserve your data, and how procedures are applied to ensure the survival of the data for the long term.

All data will be preserved and during the course of the PhD stored at the U-Drive.

After this project (March 2025), this folder will no longer be available at the U-drive. Raw Data should then be accessed through the principal investigators, and stored syntax files should be used to reproduce the study.

5.2 Describe the data you will be sharing and the repository where it will be shared?

Describe which data you will be sharing. Select where you will make your data findable and available to others. If selecting "Other" please specify below which repository and provide a URL.

Please also write below if you will apply any conditions to the re-use of your data. (i.e. Creative commons license or Data Transfer Agreement).

I will not be sharing the data further.

5.3 Are specialized, uncommon or expensive software, tools or facilities required to use the data?

Please list any specialized, uncommon or expensive software, tools or facilities that are absolutely required to obtain, use or handle your data, if any.

All data can be accessed by free, open-source or non-proprietary software.

Data Management Costs and Resources

6.1 What are the foreseeable research data management costs and how do you expect to cover them ?

Please specify the known and expected costs involved in managing, storing and sharing your data. Also explain how you plan to cover these costs.

The managing, storing and sharing is under control of the Principal Investigators. They cover the costs as well, but to the best of my knowledge no major expenses are to be expected from managing and storing this survey data.

6.2 Who will be responsible for data management?

Please specify who is responsible for updating the DMP and ensuring it is being followed accordingly.

For this specific project that is me (PhD student Luuk Mandemakers). For the whole dataset, that would be principal investigators Tanja van der Lippe and Anne van der Put.

6.3 State if you contacted an RDM consultant from Utrecht University to help you fill out your DMP.

**Please list their name and date of contact.
This is mandatory for NWO grants.**

We did not contact an RDM consultant from Utrecht University to write this Data Management Plan.

Planned Research Outputs

Text - "From Erosion to Adaptation? How Collective Job Searches Undermine Cooperation before but not After COVID-19"

This is a chapter in the dissertation of Luuk Mandemakers.

Abstract:

Over the past decades workplaces have experienced increased rates of employees that switch and search for jobs. Yet, little is known about how this affects workplaces. Existing research has so far only focused on material consequences and showed that it reduces productivity. However, workplaces are social environments in which employees cooperate to achieve goals and research on the potential erosion of workplace social fabric is scarce. This article is novel in using unique employer-employee linked data to examine whether high collective job search rates in teams erode employee cooperation. This is particularly important, as job searches are the first instance in job switch processes in which employees withdraw from their jobs, which could mark the onset of decreased employee propensities to cooperate. Moreover, combining data from 2016, 2018 and 2024, this article is able to compare these effects before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. This is important as COVID-19 radically changed the way in which many employees work and cooperate. With the shift to working from home and online collaborations, the effects of collective job searches on employee cooperation could have changed too. Results show that only before COVID-19 collective job search rates significantly eroded employee cooperation, but not after. Implications of our findings are discussed.

Text - "Quit Happens: Unravelling Which Behaviors and Attitudes of Co-Workers and Managers Trigger Turnover Contagion"

This is a chapter in the dissertation of Luuk Mandemakers.

Abstract:

A growing body of research has shown that departures of co-workers can be contagious and can spread within workplaces, leading to increased workloads, loss of control, and discontent for remaining employees. However, it is not yet fully understood how and which specific turnover behaviors and attitudes diffuse within organizations. To address this gap, this study moves beyond examining the effects of co-worker departures alone and instead compares multiple turnover behaviors and attitudes, including job searches, turnover intentions and actual departures. Additionally, to examine across whom turnover is most likely to spread, this study examines whether contagion effects are stronger when co-workers share similar job functions and demographic characteristics. Using unique employer employee linked data collected in 2024 from 1,231 employees, across 119 teams and 39 organizations in the Netherlands, this study finds that employees react more strongly to co-workers that are about to leave than to those who already departed. Moreover, the findings suggest that turnover behaviors and attitudes especially spread in employee networks when they share the same job function, gender, migrant status and educational level, but not when they are of similar age. The

implications for turnover dynamics in organizational settings are discussed.

Text - "Workplace Variation in Migrant Job Searches: Cohesion Unites, Bonuses do not Divide "

This is chapter of the dissertation of Luuk Mandemakers.

Abstract:

Dutch workplaces suffer from labor shortages and interest in diverse workforces is growing, making the retention of employees with a migration background vital. Yet, migrant employees continue to experience exclusion in the workplace, making them more prone to search for different jobs than non-migrant employees. This article is novel as it locates drivers of migrant job searches at the organizational level and examines the impact of indicators of relative distances between groups within organizations. First it assesses whether workplace cohesion mitigates differences between migrant and non-migrant employees, as cohesion may reduce intergroup distances through positive inter-ethnic contact. Second, it is examined whether workplaces that divide resources through bonus payment systems have larger job search disparities, as in such workplaces individual performance based incentives may reinforce intergroup conflict. Using unique employer-employee linked data from the Netherlands, this research finds that migrants search for jobs more often than non-migrants, that being part of cohesive workplaces as a migrant mitigates this gap and that the prevalence of bonus payment systems has no effect. To retain migrant employees and to improve the diversity of workforces, organizations should invest in increasing workplace cohesion. Further implications for theory, research and practice are discussed.

Planned research output details

Title	DOI	Type	Release date	Access level	Repository(ies)	File size	License	Metadata standard(s)	May contain sensitive data?	May contain PII?
From Erosion to Adaptation? How Collective Job Sea ...		Text	2025-04-04	Open	None specified		None specified	None specified	No	No
Quit Happens: Unravelling Which Behaviors and Atti ...		Text	2025-04-04	Open	None specified		None specified	None specified	No	No
Workplace Variation in Migrant Job Searches: Cohes ...		Text	2025-04-04	Open	None specified		None specified	None specified	No	No